

Single Crossed Bordered Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares of Order 40

Inder J. Taneja¹

Abstract

*Recently, the author constructed even order magic squares from orders 6 to 30 with different styles and models, for examples the order 20 is with 1616 magic squares, order 18 with 810 magic squares, etc. These can be seen at [31, 32, 33, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37]. The aim is to proceed for the further orders of magic squares. A systematic procedure to construct these magic squares is given. It is based on the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 etc. at **corners** and small blocks of **bordered magic rectangles** forming external borders. Then the internal borders are filled with previous known magic squares. Instead of numbers, The presentation is in figures is given for the magic squares of even orders from 22 to 40. It can be seen at [38, 39, 40, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49]. In this work we have considered **crossed bordered magic rectangles** for the magic squares of order 40. It is done with **single crossed bordered magic rectangles**. The **double crossed bordered magic rectangles** are done in another work. The work is with few examples. The pdf file of full work can be downloaded at author's site [2].*

¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012).
Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978).
E-mail: ijtaneja@gmail.com; **Web-sites:** <http://inderjtaneja.com>; <http://numbers-magic.com>;
Twitter: @IJTANEJA; **Instagram:** @crazynumbers.

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1 Introduction

The magic sums of order n of consecutive numbers from 1 to n^2 is given by

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n \times (1 + n^2)}{2}, n \geq 3. \quad (1)$$

Recently, the author [31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37] constructed magic squares of even orders from 8 to 20 using **bordered magic rectangles**. This construction is based on two aspects:

- (i) Using **magic rectangles** or **bordered magic rectangles**.
- (ii) Using algebraic formula like $(a + b)^2, a \neq b$.

For the above magic squares no construction procedure is explained. The aim is to proceed further orders of magic squares. In this work, a systematic procedure to construct these magic squares is given. It is based on the magic squares and bordered magic rectangles (BMR) of orders 4, 6, 8 etc forming external borders. Then the internal borders are filled with previous known magic squares. For the orders multiples of 4, we can always write magic squares with equal sums blocks of magic squares of order 4. This procedure is very helpful for the orders of type **2p**, where **p** is a prime number, for examples, 14, 22, 26, 34, 38, etc. For the orders like 18, 30, etc., we can make good external blocks with order 4, and for orders like 16, 20, 28, 32, etc. we can make good external borders of order 6, and so on. There is no explanations for the orders 6, 8, 10 and 12. The real construction starts from the order 14.

The whole the work is done manually, without use of any programming language, except for the constructions of small blocks of **bordered magic rectangles**. This construction is based on the software due to H. While [1]. Later, these BRMs are readopted according to distribution of each magic square. The distribution of **magic squares** or **bordered magic rectangles** is based on **half-sequential** numbers. By **half-sequential** numbers we understand that the total numbers in each case are divided in two equal parts. The first part is one sequence and the second part is another sequence. Due to **half-sequential** numbers, it is not possible to construct all orders **bordered magic rectangles**. In Appendix 3, there are tables showing the existence of these **bordered magic rectangles** for **half-sequential**. For simplicity, we shall write **BMR** as **bordered magic rectangle**. This work is for order 40. The previous works can be seen at [38, 39, 40, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49]. In this work we have considered **crossed bordered magic rectangles** for the magic squares of order 40. It is done with **single crossed bordered magic rectangles**. The **double crossed bordered magic rectangles** are done in another work. The work is with few examples. The pdf file of full work can be downloaded at author's site [2].

Remark 1. *The **bordered magic squares** and **bordered magic rectangles** are with the property that if we remove external borders in each case, still we are left with **bordered magic squares** and **bordered magic rectangles** respectively with sequential number entries. The whole work is in figures instead of numbers. In the same magic square the **small equal figures** represents equal sums **magic squares** and/or equal sums **bordered magic rectangles**.*

2 Cross-Type Magic Squares of Order 40

This section brings magic squares of order 40 in some special way, where the main bordered magic rectangles are written in **cross form**

2.1 Type 1

The crossed BMRs of order 12×20 written as two times 6×20 . The reason is that BMRs of order 12×20 don't exist for the half sequential numbers. There are total 6 examples of this kind (1-6) . Below are only 3 examples. The other examples can be seen at author's site [2].

53.

Table with 40 columns and 320 rows. Column headers are grouped under: Inder J. Taneja, https://inderjtaneja.com/, https://numbers-magic.com/, @NumbersMagic, and 32020. The table contains numerical data with several sub-rectangles highlighted in cyan.

482.

Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@NumbersMagic				32020																								
7	1596	1	1598	15	1588	9	1590	23	1580	17	1582	31	1572	25	1574	39	1564	33	1566	47	1556	41	1558	55	1548	49	1550	63	1540	57	1542	1209	400	396	1197	71	1532	65	1534	32020
2	1597	8	1595	10	1589	16	1587	18	1581	24	1579	26	1573	32	1571	34	1565	40	1563	42	1557	48	1555	50	1549	56	1547	58	1541	64	1539	383	411	1190	1218	66	1533	72	1531	32020
1600	3	1594	5	1592	11	1586	13	1584	19	1578	21	1576	27	1570	29	1568	35	1562	37	1560	43	1554	45	1552	51	1546	53	1544	59	1538	61	391	408	1193	1210	1536	67	1530	69	32020
1593	6	1599	4	1585	14	1591	12	1577	22	1583	20	1569	30	1575	28	1561	38	1567	36	1553	46	1559	44	1545	54	1551	52	1537	62	1543	60	1214	1192	409	387	1529	70	1535	68	32020
1253	339	347	1258	1255	350	338	1247	337	1261	1246	1252	358	1257	359	342	1248	1256	357	341	1250	360	263	1333	1336	262	264	1341	266	258	1342	1340	1211	419	1182	390	79	1524	73	1526	32020
356	367	364	1236	375	1225	1228	1222	1238	366	369	374	1223	377	1231	371	362	1233	1240	380	1229	1245	1344	1327	276	272	1331	269	1330	273	1326	257	394	1181	420	1207	74	1525	80	1523	32020
352	1234	1237	365	1226	376	373	379	363	1235	1232	1227	378	1224	370	1230	1239	368	361	1221	372	1249	1334	274	1325	1329	270	1332	271	1328	275	267	382	1184	417	1219	1528	75	1522	77	32020
1241	1262	1254	343	346	1251	1263	354	1264	340	355	349	1243	344	1242	1259	353	345	1244	1260	351	348	261	268	265	1339	1337	260	1335	1343	259	1338	1203	1178	423	398	1521	78	1527	76	32020
199	1404	193	1406	323	1284	1274	321	1088	515	1084	518	516	1082	1076	527	1072	530	528	1070	1064	539	1060	542	540	1058	1046	551	554	1048	552	1052	381	1194	407	1220	87	1516	81	1518	32020
194	1405	200	1403	1273	1267	334	328	1081	1078	1079	521	524	520	1069	1066	1067	533	536	532	1057	1054	1055	545	548	544	556	1042	1043	557	560	1045	1217	410	1191	384	82	1517	88	1515	32020
1408	195	1402	197	1276	336	1265	325	514	523	522	1080	1077	1087	526	535	534	1068	1065	1075	538	547	546	1056	1053	1063	1051	559	558	1044	1041	550	1202	413	1188	399	1520	83	1514	85	32020
1401	198	1407	196	322	332	1269	1279	519	1086	517	1083	1085	513	531	1074	529	1071	1073	525	543	1062	541	1059	1061	537	549	1050	1047	553	1049	555	1208	418	1183	393	1513	86	1519	84	32020
207	1396	201	1398	324	1271	330	1277	908	695	904	698	696	902	871	729	736	731	867	869	895	705	712	707	891	893	1040	566	1036	563	564	1034	402	1179	422	1199	95	1508	89	1510	32020
202	1397	208	1395	1281	329	1272	320	901	898	899	701	704	700	862	747	853	859	743	739	886	723	877	883	719	715	1033	1030	1031	569	572	568	1213	421	1180	388	90	1509	96	1507	32020
1400	203	1394	205	326	1270	331	1275	694	703	702	900	897	907	861	745	750	851	856	740	885	721	726	875	880	716	562	571	570	1032	1029	1039	403	1187	414	1198	1512	91	1506	93	32020
1393	206	1399	204	318	333	1268	1283	699	906	697	903	905	693	735	741	849	752	860	866	711	717	876	725	884	890	567	1035	565	1038	1037	561	386	415	1186	1215	1505	94	1511	92	32020
215	1388	209	1390	1282	1266	335	319	920	683	916	686	684	914	738	857	852	749	744	863	714	881	873	728	720	887	1028	575	1024	578	576	1022	1204	406	1195	397	103	1500	97	1502	32020
210	1389	216	1387	1280	317	327	1278	913	910	911	689	692	688	868	855	751	850	746	733	892	879	727	874	722	709	1021	1018	1019	581	584	580	1212	1189	412	389	98	1501	104	1499	32020
1392	211	1386	213	1121	488	484	1109	682	691	690	912	909	919	737	858	748	742	854	864	713	882	724	718	878	888	574	583	582	1020	1017	1027	401	1196	405	1200	1504	99	1498	101	32020
1385	214	1391	212	471	503	1098	1130	687	918	685	915	917	681	732	872	865	870	734	730	708	896	889	894	710	706	579	1026	577	1023	1025	573	385	424	1177	1216	1497	102	1503	100	32020
223	1380	217	1382	479	496	1105	1122	932	671	928	674	672	926	847	753	760	755	843	845	780	824	817	822	782	778	1016	587	1012	590	588	1010	1206	1185	416	395	111	1492	105	1494	32020
218	1381	224	1379	1126	1104	497	475	925	922	923	677	680	676	838	767	829	835	771	763	814	795	805	811	791	787	1009	1006	1007	593	596	592	404	1201	1205	392	106	1493	112	1491	32020
1384	219	1378	221	1123	507	1094	478	670	679	678	924	921	931	837	836	828	773	765	764	813	809	798	803	792	788	586	595	594	1008	1005	1015	283	1324	1314	281	1496	107	1490	109	32020
1377	222	1383	220	482	1093	508	1119	675	930	673	927	929	669	759	768	775	826	833	842	783	793	804	797	808	818	591	1014	589	1011	1013	585	1313	1307	294	288	1489	110	1495	108	32020
231	1372	225	1374	470	1096	505	1131	944	659	660	662	940	938	844	832	774	827	769	757	786	789	801	800	812	815	1004	1000	599	602	600	998	1316	296	1305	285	119	1484	113	1486	32020
226	1373	232	1371	1115	1090	511	486	937	934	935	665	668	664	762	770	825	776	831	839	820	807	799	802	794	781	997	994	995	605	608	604	282	292	1309	1319	114	1485	120	1483	32020
1376	227	1370	229	469	1106	495	1132	658	667	666	936	933	943	761	830	772	766	834	840	785	810	796	790	806	816	598	607	606	996	993	1003	284	1311	290	1317	1488	115	1482	117	32020
1369	230	1375	228	1129	498	1103	472	663	942	941	939	661	657	756	848	841	846	758	754	823	777	784	779	819	821	603	601	1002	999	1001	597	1321	289	1312	280	1481	118	1487	116	32020
239	1364	233	1366	491	501	1100	1110	956	647	952	650	648	950	968	635	964	638	636	962	980	623	976	626	624	974	992	611	988	614	612	986	286	1310	291	1315	127	1476	121	1478	32020
234	1365	240	1363	1120	506	1095	481	949	946	947	653	656	652	961	958	959	641	644	640	973	970	971	629	632	628	985	982	983	617	620	616	278	293	1308	1323	122	1477	128	1475	32020
1368	235	1362	237	490	1091	510	1111	646	655	654	948	945	955	634	643	642	960	957	967	622	631	630	972	969	979	610	619	618	984	981	991	1322	1306	295	279	1480	123	1474	125	32020
1361	238	1367	236	1125	509	1092	476	651	954	649	951	953	645	639	966	637	963	965	633	627	978	625	975	977	621	615	990	613	987	989	609	1320	277	287	1318	1473	126	1479	124	32020
247	1356	241	1358	1114	1099	502	487	303	1293	1296	302	304	1301	306	298	1302	1300	1165	427	435	1170	1167	438	426	1159	425	1173	447	1164	446	1169	1158	430	1160	1168	445	429	1162	448	32020
242	1357	248	1355	474	499	1102	1127	1304	1287	316	312	1291	309	1290	313	1286	297	444	459	452	1148	463	1137	1140	1134	1150	454	1143	462	1135	465	457	455	450	1145	1152	468	1141	1157	32020
1360	243	1354	245	1116	494	1107	485	1294	314	1285	1289	310	1292	311	1288	315	307	440	1142	1149	453	1138	464	461</																

Order of Magic Square	Bordered Magic Rectangles
6	4×6
8	6×8
10	$4 \times 10, 8 \times 10$
12	$6 \times 12, 10 \times 12$
14	$4 \times 14, 8 \times 14, 12 \times 14$
16	$6 \times 16, 10 \times 16, 14 \times 16$
18	$4 \times 18, 8 \times 18, 12 \times 18$
20	$6 \times 20, 10 \times 20, 14 \times 20, 18 \times 20$
22	$4 \times 22, 8 \times 22, 12 \times 22,$ $16 \times 22, 20 \times 22$
24	$6 \times 24, 10 \times 24, 14 \times 24,$ $18 \times 24, 22 \times 24$
26	$4 \times 26, 8 \times 26, 12 \times 26,$ $16 \times 26, 20 \times 26, 24 \times 26$
28	$6 \times 28, 10 \times 28, 14 \times 28,$ $18 \times 28, 22 \times 28, 26 \times 28$
30	$4 \times 30, 8 \times 30, 12 \times 30, 16 \times 30,$ $20 \times 30, 24 \times 30, 28 \times 30$
32	$6 \times 32, 10 \times 32, 14 \times 32, 18 \times 32,$ $22 \times 32, 26 \times 32, 30 \times 32$
34	$4 \times 34, 8 \times 34, 12 \times 34, 16 \times 34,$ $20 \times 34, 24 \times 34, 28 \times 34, 32 \times 34$

Order of Magic Square	Bordered Magic Rectangles
36	$6 \times 36, 10 \times 36, 14 \times 36, 18 \times 36,$ $22 \times 36, 26 \times 36, 30 \times 36, 34 \times 36$
38	$4 \times 38, 8 \times 38, 12 \times 38, 16 \times 38, 20 \times 38,$ $24 \times 38, 28 \times 38, 32 \times 38, 36 \times 38$
40	$6 \times 40, 10 \times 40, 14 \times 40, 18 \times 40, 22 \times 40,$ $26 \times 40, 30 \times 40, 34 \times 40, 38 \times 40$
42	$4 \times 42, 8 \times 42, 12 \times 42, 16 \times 42, 20 \times 42,$ $24 \times 42, 28 \times 42, 32 \times 42, 36 \times 42, 40 \times 42$
44	$6 \times 44, 10 \times 44, 14 \times 44, 18 \times 44, 22 \times 44, 26 \times 44,$ $30 \times 44, 34 \times 44, 38 \times 44, 42 \times 44$
46	$4 \times 46, 8 \times 46, 12 \times 46, 16 \times 46, 20 \times 46, 24 \times 46,$ $28 \times 46, 32 \times 46, 36 \times 46, 40 \times 46, 44 \times 46$
48	$6 \times 48, 10 \times 48, 14 \times 48, 18 \times 48, 22 \times 48, 26 \times 48,$ $30 \times 48, 34 \times 48, 38 \times 48, 42 \times 48, 46 \times 48$
50	$4 \times 50, 8 \times 50, 12 \times 50, 16 \times 50, 20 \times 50, 24 \times 50,$ $28 \times 50, 32 \times 50, 36 \times 50, 40 \times 50, 44 \times 50, 48 \times 50$

4 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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